

RARE
DISEASES
INTERNATIONAL

GLOBAL NETWORK
FOR RARE DISEASES

GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES ON RARE DISEASE CENTERS: What We Learned from Case Studies

REPORT
March 2026

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	3
METHODOLOGY	6
Aga Khan University, Genetic Disorders Care Program - Karachi - Pakistan	9
Hospital Pediátrico Baca Ortiz - Quito - Ecuador	12
Peking Union Medical College Hospital- Beijing - China	15
Sant Joan de Déu - Barcelona - Spain	18
Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital - Cape Town - South Africa	21
Ramathibodi Hospital - Bangkok - Thailand	24
Human Genetics and Genome Research Institute, National Research Centre - Cairo - Egypt	27
Gillette Children's Hospital - St. Paul - USA	30
CONCLUSION	33

INTRODUCTION

Over the past years, Rare Diseases International (RDI) has undertaken a progressive effort to better understand the global rare disease landscape, with a particular focus on the systems, structures, and actors involved in delivering care to people living with rare diseases (PLWRD). Through continuous engagement with patient representatives, clinicians, and experts across regions, RDI has sought to map existing resources, identify gaps, and support more coordinated and equitable approaches to rare disease care worldwide. This work led to the publication of the first edition of the *Resource Maps* in the second quarter of 2024.

The Resource Maps provided an initial overview of the rare disease landscape in multiple countries, focusing on three core areas: the policy environment, healthcare systems, and patient organizations. By consolidating qualitative insights from diverse contexts, this first phase of data collection offered an understanding of available resources and highlighted persistent challenges affecting access to diagnosis, care, and support for PLWRD.

Building on this initial work, RDI conducted a *Global Survey* in the third and fourth quarters of 2024 to update and expand the Resource Maps. This survey aimed to identify experts, centers and networks dedicated to rare diseases, as well as mapping their characteristics, scope of expertise, and collaboration practices. The findings were compiled in a dedicated report, providing an overview of rare disease expertise and care structures across countries and regions.

While survey data offered a broad overview, it could not fully capture the diversity of how rare disease centers are organized and operate within different health system contexts.

To address this gap, RDI initiated a *Qualitative Case Study Project* to explore selected rare disease centers in greater depth. Through semi-structured interviews with experts and managers, this case series aims to provide richer insights into governance models, service organization, patient engagement, research activities, and collaboration practices. Rather than producing a comparative assessment, the purpose of this report is to present examples that reflect the diversity of rare disease centers worldwide and to highlight practices, challenges, and enabling factors that may inform future policy, planning, and international collaboration.

Why Develop Case Studies on Rare Disease Centers?

- Explore different models of rare disease centers across diverse contexts, gaining insight into how they are structured, operate, and address challenges
- Generate evidence for scalability and replication by identifying models adaptable to different regions, including low-resource settings, and showcasing innovative practices that can inspire others
- Understand integration with existing health systems, including links with primary care, referral systems, and national programmes (e.g. newborn screening)
- Support the development of standards, guidelines, and monitoring and evaluation frameworks, including recommendations for the establishment and strengthening of new centers
- Strengthen advocacy and visibility by providing evidence to engage stakeholders – including policymakers, funders, and civil society – and contribute to broader policy discussions
- Identify opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange between centers across countries, contributing to the development of the Global Network for Rare Diseases

Mapping Rare Disease Ecosystems: Timeline and Milestones

CONDUCTED PUBLIC SURVEY

Focus on rare disease

- Expertise
- Centers
- Networks

Apr 2024

PUBLISHED RESOURCE MAPS

3 critical areas:

- policy landscape
- healthcare systems
- patient organizations

Oct 2024

PUBLISHED REPORT ON SURVEY RESULTS

228 SURVEYS
from
63 COUNTRIES

Feb 2025

CONDUCTED CASE STUDY PROJECT

Interviewed 8 centers from different countries

- structure and functioning
- care delivery
- recognition
- collaboration

Sept 2025

REPORT on CASE STUDIES

**GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES ON RARE DISEASE CENTERS:
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March 2026

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METHODOLOGY

Study design

This project was designed as a qualitative case series focusing on rare disease centers operating in different geographic regions and healthcare system contexts. The goal was to develop a collection of 8–10 case reports that document how rare disease centers are structured, organized, and integrated within national and international health systems. The case studies are intended to be illustrative rather than comparative, showcasing diverse models of care and organizational approaches.

Selection of centers

Centers were identified through a two-step selection process. In the first phase, potential centers were selected from respondents to the 2024 Rare Disease Expertise Survey who reported being involved in the delivery or coordination of rare disease care. This ensured alignment between the case studies and the broader mapping work conducted by RDI. In the second phase, selected centers were contacted to assess their interest and availability to participate in the case study project. Final inclusion was based on willingness to participate, geographic diversity, and representation of different healthcare system contexts.

In total, eight centers were included in this report, with the intention of reflecting a broad range of organizational models, levels of formal recognition, and integration within national and international networks.

Data collection

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews conducted with experts and managers from each selected center. A semi-structured interview guide was used to ensure consistency across interviews while allowing flexibility for participants to elaborate on topics most relevant to their context.

Interviews explored the following key areas:

- Governance and organization, including structural models, funding sources, and sustainability
- Recognition and accreditation processes at national or international levels
- Service delivery and care coordination
- Patient engagement and support, including the role of PLWRD and patient organizations
- Research and innovation activities, such as clinical trials and data collection
- Collaboration and networking at national, regional, and international levels
- Key challenges and unmet needs related to funding, workforce, infrastructure, and access to medicines
- Future perspectives, including opportunities for improvement and scaling up successful practices

Data analysis

Interview transcripts and detailed notes were reviewed and analyzed using a thematic, descriptive approach. Rather than applying a comparative framework, data were grouped and synthesized to highlight the unique characteristics of each center, including their organizational models, areas of expertise, and modes of integration within healthcare systems and networks. The analysis focused on identifying key features, challenges, and innovative practices within each case, with the aim of presenting rich, contextualized descriptions rather than drawing comparisons across centers. This approach allowed the case studies to showcase diversity in how rare disease centers operate, respond to local constraints, and develop solutions tailored to their specific contexts. Common themes were used to structure the narratives, while preserving the individuality of each center and emphasizing lessons that may be informative or inspiring for other settings.

CENTERS

- Karachi, Pakistan – Aga Khan University, Genetic Disorders Care Program
- Quito, Ecuador – Hospital Pediátrico Baca Ortiz
- Beijing, China – Peking Union Medical College Hospital (PUMCH)
- Barcelona, Spain – Sant Joan de Déu
- Cape Town, South Africa – Red Cross War Memorial Children’s Hospital
- Bangkok, Thailand – Ramathibodi Hospital
- Cairo, Egypt – Human Genetics and Genome Research Institute
- St. Paul, Minnesota, USA – Gillette Children’s Hospital

AGA KHAN UNIVERSITY GENETIC DISORDERS CARE PROGRAM - KARACHI, PAKISTAN

Aga Khan University (AKU) hosts a private, not-for-profit academic health system integrating care, teaching, and research. Within this setting, its genetics and genomics service has evolved into a rare-disease-focused multidisciplinary team—still uncommon nationally—and serves as a key point of expertise in a context with limited formal structures and scarce genetics capacity.

Beyond expertise, the team provides a reliable “front door” for families navigating a complex system, with coordinated roles covering clinical evaluation, counselling, testing, interpretation, follow-up, and care navigation.

Operating in a context of limited coverage and high out-of-pocket costs

The center works in a national context where most specialized care is financed through out-of-pocket payment, with no universal health coverage for the majority of people requiring rare disease care. At AKU, patients commonly pay for consultations and, critically, for genetic tests that are often sent abroad. To partially reduce financial barriers, the hospital can draw on a welfare fund supported by charitable giving. This support may help cover hospital-based clinical care (including admissions), and in some cases may cover a significant portion of costs for families assessed as eligible. In addition, the center has occasionally accessed ad hoc philanthropic support specifically for genetic testing, while working toward a longer-term goal of establishing a more sustainable endowment-type fund for rare disease-related costs.

“Unrecognized” formally - yet functioning as a national and regional reference point

Pakistan has no government mechanism to designate centers of expertise for rare diseases. The center is therefore not formally recognized by national authorities as a rare disease center.

Despite the absence of official designation, AKU functions de facto as a national referral center, receiving patients from hospitals across Pakistan and neighboring countries (Afghanistan, Iran, and the Gulf), and offering teleconsultations when travel or cost is prohibitive.

Multidisciplinary Team: Building Capacity for Complex Care

AKU's model integrates two genetic counsellors, an advanced clinical genomics nurse from the fetal-maternal unit, and links to molecular genetics research. Weekly breast cancer tumor boards ensure genetics is embedded in oncology decision-making, while periodical molecular case conferences bring together clinical genetics, research genetics, and laboratory staff to resolve variant interpretation and tough diagnostic questions. In addition, perinatal genetics case conferences convene obstetrics, neonatology, and genetics teams to co-plan care for identified fetal anomalies and prepare families for delivery at the appropriate level of care.

A low-cost, high-impact innovation: helplines as a safety net

With many patients travelling from outside the institution and living far from the hospital, care navigation cannot rely solely on in-person interactions. To address this challenge, AKU has established WhatsApp-based helplines – including a general genetics line and dedicated perinatal lines – managed by team members to triage questions, coordinate appointments, and maintain communication with referring clinicians.

These helplines provide a “safety net” for families who might otherwise leave the clinic without a clear ongoing point of contact. This model is simple yet strategic.

It strengthens follow-up, reduces

loss to follow-up, and supports families between appointments in a context where travel and repeat visits can be financially and logistically challenging.

Patient Engagement: Emerging and Essential

Structured patient organizations remain rare in Pakistan due to stigma and limited awareness, but AKU is laying groundwork for systematic engagement. The team currently collects feedback informally and is working towards

developing more structured methods to assess patient experiences with genetic counselling and care pathways.

Our patients often take advocacy into their own hands—creating networks and resources we could never build alone.

Patients need a central contact. When they leave the hospital, they are a little bit lost—our helplines keep them connected.

Individual patient advocates have begun to lead initiatives—such as translating educational materials into Urdu and creating disease-specific WhatsApp groups for Spinal Muscular Atrophy, Huntington’s disease and Epidermolysis bullosa.

A Prevention-First Vision in a High-Consanguinity Population

AKU places prevention at the center of its rare disease strategy, reflecting the high burden of autosomal recessive conditions linked to consanguinity. In clinical practice, multiple affected siblings within the same family are a common pattern.

The center prioritizes raising community awareness of genetic risk, particularly in relation to cousin marriage, where understanding and access to counselling and testing remain limited. To address this, AKU is strengthening pathways for preconception counselling, carrier testing where feasible, and prenatal and perinatal genetics services, including greater integration within maternal-fetal care.

Research Rooted in Local Needs

AKU’s research aligns with national priorities, addressing the high burden of autosomal recessive conditions linked to consanguinity. Early work on gene-editing for beta thalassemia and sickle cell disease reflects a focus on long-term impact.

The center contributes through clinical research and is expanding into patient experience, genetic counselling, and quality of life. While not yet involved in clinical trials due to limited visibility and industry presence, AKU has established a REDCap registry to support cohort identification and future trial readiness.

Leveraging National and International Partnerships

In the absence of formal national networks, AKU prioritizes international collaboration, including participation in UDNI and disease-specific consortia, to access expertise and support complex case management.

These partnerships also strengthen workforce capacity. National collaboration remains informal, with no unified registry. AKU is addressing this through its internal registry and exploring data-sharing initiatives, positioning itself as both a care provider and a connector to global expertise.

HOSPITAL PEDIÁTRICO BACA ORTIZ - QUITO, ECUADOR

Baca Ortiz Hospital is a pediatric public hospital in Quito and it is one of Ecuador's largest pediatric referral institutions and delivers specialized care to children with complex and rare conditions across the country. Operating under the Ministry of Public Health, the hospital provides services within the public healthcare system and ensures access to care regardless of socioeconomic status.

A Pioneering National Hub for Pediatric Rare Diseases

The Rare Disease Unit was established following a national policy initiative launched in 2023 to strengthen recognition and coordination of rare disease care. The government mandated the creation of rare disease units in Ecuador's two largest pediatric hospitals, located in Quito and Guayaquil. Although still under development, the Quito unit already functions as a national referral hub for pediatric rare diseases and genetic conditions, providing diagnostic expertise and multidisciplinary management for patients from across the country.

The unit (Unidad de Vigilancia para personas con Enfermedades Raras – UVER) is led by a core clinical team composed of two medical geneticists, one metabolic pediatrician, and one pediatric neurologist. This group coordinates care, facilitates diagnostic pathways, and leads service development. To support multidisciplinary management, the team has established collaborations with specialists from multiple pediatric subspecialties, including cardiology, orthopedics, and other clinical departments. In total, approximately fifteen healthcare professionals contribute to rare disease care through this collaborative structure.

The unit does not yet operate as a physically separate service within the hospital. Rare disease care is integrated into existing outpatient clinics, inpatient services, and specialist referral pathways. Weekly multidisciplinary meetings are held to review complex cases, allowing coordinated decision-making across specialties. In addition, disease-specific clinical working groups are being developed, particularly for metabolic and neurometabolic disorders and skeletal dysplasia, with the aim of strengthening care coordination and improving long-term patient follow-up.

Building Diagnostic and Data Infrastructure for Rare Disease Care

Access to accurate and timely diagnosis has historically represented a significant challenge for rare disease care in Ecuador. Diagnostic services were previously limited, primarily relying on cytogenetic testing, which left many patients without confirmed diagnoses and constrained opportunities for appropriate clinical management, surveillance, and data generation.

In recent years, diagnostic capacity has expanded through access to next-generation sequencing technologies, including whole exome sequencing, enabled through collaboration with external public laboratories. Although these tests are not conducted directly within the hospital, clinical teams play a central role in coordinating testing requests, interpreting results, and integrating diagnostic findings into patient care pathways.

The strengthening of diagnostic services has also supported more systematic documentation of confirmed rare disease cases. To support this, the clinical team established a locally managed data collection system, ensuring continuity in case identification, documentation, and data monitoring. In addition, the hospital collaborates closely with other institutions within the Ministry of Health network, including an adult public hospital where exome sequencing analyses are performed and a national genetics laboratory providing cytogenetic testing services. These partnerships enable coordinated delivery of diagnostic services across institutions and contribute to strengthening rare disease care within the public healthcare system.

Delivering Care Across Diverse and Underserved Regions

The hospital receives referrals from across Ecuador, including remote and rural areas such as communities located in the Amazon area, where access to specialized care and rehabilitation services remains limited. Many patients therefore remain under long-term follow-up at the hospital rather than transitioning fully to local services. To improve continuity of care, the clinical team has initiated a teleconsultation programme with Latacunga Hospital as a pilot and plans to expand coordination with other regional hospitals. These programmes allow local pediatricians to receive specialist input for complex cases and help reduce the burden of repeated long-distance travel for families, some of whom must travel up to ten hours to access specialized services. Care coordination extends beyond clinical management.

Social workers support families by facilitating access to rehabilitation services and social assistance programmes available within their local communities. Access to rehabilitation remains uneven across regions, particularly for families living in remote areas with limited healthcare infrastructure.

Information sharing between healthcare facilities remains constrained by the absence of a unified national electronic health record system. Despite this limitation, the team continues to explore solutions to improve communication between tertiary and regional providers.

Patient Organization Support as a Key Resource

Psychological support is available within the hospital through dedicated mental health professionals who support patients and families throughout the diagnostic and care process. Access to psychological and social support outside the hospital varies depending on local service availability.

Several patient organizations operate at the national level for specific rare diseases, including mucopolysaccharidoses and osteogenesis imperfecta. These organizations support families in treatment access advocacy, legal assistance, and transportation support for patients traveling long distances for specialized care. Collaboration between the hospital and patient organizations is present but remains informal due to workforce and time constraints.

Developing Research Capacity

Research activities at the center are currently in early stages and focus primarily on case reports and clinical data collection. The Rare Disease Unit collaborates with multiple universities in Quito to establish research groups focused on genetic and rare disease conditions. As diagnostic data expands, the team anticipates developing broader research programmes addressing epidemiological patterns, neurodevelopmental disorders, and other locally relevant rare disease conditions. These initiatives aim to strengthen national evidence generation and support improvements in clinical practice and public health planning. The center maintains professional collaborations both nationally and internationally. Internationally, clinicians maintain active relationships with academic and clinical institutions in Latin America and North America. These collaborations support case consultations, diagnostic interpretation, and professional training opportunities. Philanthropic partnerships have also facilitated international exchanges and knowledge sharing.

PEKING UNION MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL - BEIJING, CHINA

Peking Union Medical College Hospital (PUMCH) is a national public tertiary hospital and the teaching hospital of Peking Union Medical College. As one of China's leading academic medical institutions, PUMCH integrates clinical care, education, and research within a unified framework. The hospital is funded primarily through national government allocations, medical insurance reimbursements, and competitive research grants.

Driving National Coordination for Rare Disease Care

In 2019, PUMCH was designated by the National Health Commission as the national lead hospital for China's Rare Disease Diagnosis and Treatment Collaboration Network. This network represents a major national initiative aimed at strengthening diagnosis, referral systems, and treatment coordination for rare diseases across the country.

Initially composed of 324 hospitals, including one national lead hospital, 32 provincial lead hospitals, and 291 member hospitals, the network expanded to 419 hospitals by 2024, reflecting rapid national scale-up and growing recognition of rare diseases as a public health priority.

Hospitals participating in the network are selected based on demonstrated expertise in rare disease diagnosis and treatment, clinical caseload, and institutional capacity. The selection process involves recommendations from provincial health commissions followed by national expert review. To maintain consistent quality of care, both national and provincial health authorities conduct regular performance and quality assessments of participating institutions.

Through its leadership role, PUMCH supports national referral pathways, professional training programmes, and knowledge exchange among institutions. This coordinated model aims to standardize rare disease care delivery across regions while strengthening local diagnostic and treatment capacity. In a healthcare system characterized by significant geographic diversity and population scale, this structured approach seeks to reduce disparities in access to specialized care and promote earlier and more accurate diagnosis nationwide.

The “PUMCH Model”: Integrated, Multidisciplinary, Patient-Centered

PUMCH has developed a multidisciplinary integrated care framework for rare diseases, known as the “PUMCH Model,” combining outpatient, inpatient, and consultation services into a coordinated system to address complex, multi-system conditions. At its center is the Medical Center for Rare Diseases, which oversees clinical care, research, and external collaboration.

In outpatient care, a multidisciplinary rare disease clinic brings together specialists from multiple departments in a shared setting. Supported by an inter-departmental referral system, patients can access multiple specialties after an initial consultation without repeated registration. The clinic includes 22 specialties and over 60 physicians.

For inpatient care, PUMCH operates a dedicated rare disease ward with a dual admission pathway—either through specialty departments or the centralized Rare Diseases Department for complex, multi-system cases. The inpatient team spans multiple disciplines, including rheumatology, hematology, neurology, endocrinology, dermatology, and general practice.

Together, these integrated pathways improve continuity of care, reduce fragmentation, and support coordinated clinical decision-making tailored to the needs of people living with rare diseases.

Advanced Multidisciplinary Consultation and Case Coordination

To support the management of complex cases, PUMCH has established structured multidisciplinary team (MDT) rounds alongside clinical, genetic, and basic science case discussions. All admitted patients are included in clinical cohorts to support long-term follow-up and disease management. The Rare Disease MDT Consultation Center plays a central role in coordinating consultations for complex or difficult-to-diagnose cases referred both internally and by medical institutions across China. The center maintains a national consultation expert database comprising more than 400 experts across 44 specialties, ensuring rapid access to specialized expertise. To optimize the MDT process, PUMCH has established governance structures defining which departments can request and provide consultations, ensuring appropriate case selection and clinical value. Administrative assistants play a key coordination role, organizing consultations, facilitating information exchange, scheduling meetings, and supporting smooth MDT operations.

Holistic Patient Support and Engagement

PUMCH incorporates structured patient and family engagement mechanisms into service delivery. Patient feedback is collected through interviews, questionnaire surveys, routine satisfaction assessments, and dedicated communication channels such as hospital hotlines and digital platforms. Insights generated through these channels are used to improve clinical workflows, enhance patient experience, and guide service redesign initiatives. Psychological counselling and social work services are integrated across both outpatient and inpatient settings to support patients and families throughout the diagnostic and treatment journey. Patient navigation services are also available to assist individuals in coordinating appointments, accessing healthcare resources, and navigating complex care pathways.

These comprehensive support services aim to address not only clinical needs but also the psychosocial and practical challenges frequently experienced by individuals living with rare diseases and their families.

Advancing Knowledge, Data, and Global Collaboration

Research and data generation are central pillars of PUMCH's rare disease strategy. The hospital actively leads and participates in clinical trials aimed at improving diagnostic approaches and therapeutic interventions. As in many rare disease contexts, recruitment challenges linked to small patient populations and the need to balance data sharing with patient privacy remain ongoing considerations.

PUMCH also plays a leading national role in rare disease data infrastructure through its management of China's National Rare Diseases Registry System, which currently includes more than 100,000 registered cases. This registry provides a critical foundation for research, policy development, and improved clinical understanding of rare diseases.

Beyond research, PUMCH strengthens collaboration both nationally and internationally. Domestically, the hospital leads the Rare Disease Diagnosis and Treatment Collaboration Network, facilitating referrals, professional training, and coordinated research across China. Internationally, PUMCH contributes to global rare disease efforts, including collaboration with the International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDiRC), supporting knowledge exchange and global research alignment.

SANT JOAN DE DEU BARCELONA, SPAIN

Hospital Sant Joan de Déu Barcelona (SJD) is a leading center for rare diseases. The hospital provides care for a large and diverse population of children and adolescents living with rare diseases, supported by multiple highly specialized clinical units and cross-cutting programmes. Given the scale and complexity of this activity, SJD has prioritized organizational models that enable coordination across specialties, continuity over time, and alignment between care, research, and innovation.

Accreditation as a catalyst for Excellence

SJD is formally recognized at regional, national, and European levels, reflecting both the breadth and depth of its rare disease expertise. At the regional level, the hospital is integrated within Catalan rare disease networks, which are designed to coordinate care, support territorial hospitals, and facilitate knowledge transfer across the healthcare system. At the national level, SJD holds multiple reference designations from the Spanish Ministry of Health, acknowledging its role in delivering highly specialized, multidisciplinary care for rare and complex conditions and in ensuring equitable access for patients across the country. At the European level, the hospital is extensively involved in European Reference Networks (ERNs), participating in the majority of ERNs and contributing to cross-border collaboration through virtual consultations, shared clinical guidelines, registries, and research activities. Accreditation is not treated as a mere formality at SJD; it is a catalyst for transformation. The hospital holds recognition at regional, national, and European levels and these accreditations impose rigorous standards—mandatory case managers, formal transition protocols, and registry participation that have reshaped care delivery.

This commitment ensures that accreditation translates into tangible improvements for patients and families.

It's not just about being recognized. The accreditation is what forces the hospital to do things that have been recommended.

Coordinating complexity Through Integrated Care

SJD manages rare disease care across more than 2000 conditions and follows over 22000 active patients living with rare diseases. To address this level of complexity, the hospital has invested in models that go beyond sequential multidisciplinary referrals toward interdisciplinary decision-making. Clinical teams participate in regular cross-specialty discussions, often supported by digital tools, allowing cases to be reviewed collectively without requiring families to attend multiple appointments. Decisions are integrated into shared electronic medical records, ensuring transparency and continuity across departments and enabling other professionals—and, where appropriate, families through patient portals—to access agreed care plans. Digital infrastructure is also used to collect patient-reported outcomes and quality-of-life measures remotely. This allows teams to identify clinical and psychosocial risks early, prioritize follow-up, and tailor referrals, including to psychological support services. These tools reduce unnecessary hospital visits while strengthening monitoring for complex and chronic conditions.

Patients and Families as Partners

Patient and family engagement is embedded across SJD's organizational structures and improvement processes. Families are not passive recipients of care; they are active contributors to service design and improvement. The hospital operates Patient and Family Councils, which provide structured input into hospital priorities and decision-making. A continuous feedback system collects patient and family input following clinical encounters. Feedback is analyzed through regular dashboards shared with services, allowing the identification of recurring challenges and areas for improvement.

When patterns emerge, targeted improvement projects are initiated through structured interviews, focus groups, and co-design sessions involving patients, families, and professionals. This approach extends beyond service improvement to strategic and infrastructural design.

***Patients are a lever of change.
We involve them from macro to micro.***

Families have been actively involved in the planning of new facilities dedicated to rare and complex diseases, contributing to decisions on care pathways, navigation, information provision, privacy, waiting areas, and common spaces.

Digital Tools Enabling Coordination, Monitoring, and Continuity

SJD leverages advanced digital infrastructure to enhance coordination and patient experience. The hospital uses a secure patient portal and mobile applications to enable families to access care plans, upload data, and communicate with clinical teams. These platforms allow remote collection of patient-reported outcomes, including quality-of-life indicators, anxiety, and depression screening, which helps clinicians identify psychosocial risks early and prioritize interventions. Virtual case conferences are integrated into electronic medical records, ensuring that interdisciplinary decisions are documented and accessible to all relevant professionals. Telemedicine consultations reduce unnecessary travel for families, while digital dashboards provide real-time feedback to services, supporting continuous improvement.

Where Care and Research Converge

Research is a central component of SJD's rare disease model. The hospital conducts more than 300 active clinical research studies, including over 230 clinical trials, with rare diseases representing the 68% of this activity. In pediatric settings, participation in clinical research often constitutes the only available therapeutic option for children with conditions lacking approved treatments. SJD combines industry-sponsored trials with a substantial portfolio of academic research supported by public funding, charities, and patient organizations. The hospital has developed extensive expertise in advanced therapies, including gene therapies, and treats children from Spain and other countries through early-phase and innovative studies.

Patients and families are engaged in research processes, including protocol review and the development of patient-facing materials, with specific attention to reducing the burden of participation on daily life, education, and family responsibilities. Disease registries and digital platforms enable patients to contribute data and remain informed about research progress, strengthening trust and relevance.

RED CROSS WAR MEMORIAL CHILDREN'S HOSPITAL - CAPE TOWN, SOUTH AFRICA

Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital is a public tertiary pediatric hospital operating within South Africa's national public healthcare system. The hospital serves as a major referral center for complex pediatric conditions, including rare diseases, within a healthcare system characterized by strong public sector reliance and significant resource constraints. Although not formally designated as a rare disease center, the hospital functions as a national referral hub for complex pediatric cases due to its specialist workforce and its role as one of the country's primary public pediatric tertiary institutions.

Rare Disease Care in a Public Tertiary Hospital

The hospital operates within South Africa's predominantly public healthcare system, where care is largely government-funded and accessible to patients regardless of their ability to pay. While a small proportion of patients access care through private insurance schemes, the majority of families receiving services rely on publicly funded healthcare.

South Africa's health system follows a tiered referral model consisting of primary care clinics, district hospitals, and tertiary hospitals. Within this structure, Red Cross Children's Hospital receives patients with complex and difficult-to-diagnose conditions referred from lower-level facilities when management or diagnostic capacity exceeds local capabilities. Rare diseases are therefore managed as part of the hospital's broader responsibility for complex pediatric care rather than through a dedicated rare disease service.

The hospital is not formally recognized by national authorities as a center of expertise for rare diseases. Instead, specialist recognition occurs at the level of professional accreditation through the Health Professions Council of South Africa (HPCSA), which regulates specialist training and professional standards. As a result, the hospital's rare disease expertise is shaped primarily by the availability of specialist disciplines rather than through a coordinated national designation or accreditation framework for rare disease centers.

Specialist-Led Multidisciplinary Care

As a tertiary pediatric hospital, care is delivered across multiple subspecialties, with multidisciplinary collaboration for children with complex and multi-system conditions, including rare diseases. Referrals between specialties are coordinated internally, and many patients are followed by multiple teams. This model enables access to diverse expertise within the same institution and supports comprehensive clinical assessment.

However, coordination remains largely clinician-driven, with no formal case management or patient navigation roles. Clinicians initiate referrals, and families are responsible for attending appointments across services, which can create logistical and administrative burdens when managing complex care pathways.

Continuity of care beyond the hospital is supported through links with primary healthcare centers, although referral pathways are often based on geographic availability rather than formal shared-care protocols. Clinical management protocols are typically developed within individual specialties, with some departments (e.g., dermatology) having condition-specific approaches, but no overarching hospital-wide rare disease care pathway or coordination framework. Similarly, data systems and registries are specialty-driven. For example, cardiology maintains a congenital heart disease registry linked to research, alongside separate registries in genetics and oncology. These initiatives operate independently, reflecting how data collection and care organization vary across disciplines and highlighting the absence of a unified institutional or national rare disease data system.

Patient Support and Engagement: Emerging Through Disease-Specific Initiatives

Patient and family support mechanisms are largely driven by individual specialties and patient advocacy initiatives rather than formal hospital-wide programs. Within dermatology, several patient support organizations have been established, including groups supporting epidermolysis bullosa, eczema, psoriasis, and hidradenitis suppurativa. These organizations provide peer support, information sharing, and advocacy for affected families.

Support group availability varies significantly across disease areas and remains limited overall. Psychological and social support services are available within clinical care pathways but are not consistently integrated across all rare disease services.

Advancing Diagnosis and Research in a Resource-Limited Setting

Research activity at Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital spans multiple specialties and includes participation in clinical trials and international collaborations. However, most research efforts focus on more common pediatric conditions, with rare disease studies typically undertaken on a case-by-case basis. These initiatives are often driven by individual clinician expertise or external partnership opportunities rather than through dedicated institutional rare disease research programmes.

Diagnostic capacity represents a significant challenge. While genetics services exist within South Africa, access to advanced molecular testing remains limited, frequently requiring biological samples to be sent to international laboratories for confirmation of suspected genetic conditions. This approach can result in delays and create financial barriers, ultimately affecting timely diagnosis and clinical decision-making.

Broader system-level constraints also influence rare disease care delivery. Limited availability of advanced diagnostic technologies, combined with shortages of specialized treatments, medical supplies, and disease-specific services, continues to restrict the hospital's ability to provide comprehensive care for certain rare conditions.

The biggest hurdle is access to genetics. We do have a genetics unit, but it mainly provides advice and helps us send samples abroad. We cannot test and confirm some of these rare diseases in South Africa.

Connecting Expertise Through Informal Networks

Formal national rare disease networks or structured referral systems between centers of expertise are not currently established in South Africa. Collaboration instead occurs primarily through professional relationships, training networks, and clinician-led communication across institutions. Many clinicians maintain international academic and clinical connections developed through fellowships or specialist training abroad, which support consultation, knowledge exchange, and case discussions for complex conditions.

These collaborations play an important role in facilitating diagnostic clarification and supporting research activities, particularly for undiagnosed or highly specialized rare disease cases. However, they remain largely dependent on individual professional relationships rather than being supported by formal institutional partnerships or coordinated national and international referral frameworks.

RAMATHIBODI HOSPITAL RARE DISEASE CENTER – BANGKOK, THAILAND

Ramathibodi Hospital, part of the Faculty of Medicine at Mahidol University, is an academic public hospital providing specialized care for people living with rare diseases in Thailand. Although operating as a public institution, the hospital falls under the Ministry of Higher Education rather than the Ministry of Health. The center receives referrals from both public and private hospitals nationwide and provides services to patients covered under Thailand's Universal Coverage (UC) Scheme, Social Security system (SSS), and Civil Servant Medical Benefit Scheme (CSMBS). The Rare Disease Center operates within the Division of Medical Genetics under the Department of Pediatrics and functions as a national hub for genetic diagnostics and management.

A Hybrid Funding Model Supporting Access to Genetic Services

Rare disease services at Ramathibodi are primarily financed through Thailand's Universal Coverage system, which reimburses genetic testing and treatments included in the national benefit package. This structure enables equitable access to many essential diagnostic and clinical services.

However, advanced genetic testing, including genome and exome sequencing, remains outside the national reimbursement framework. To address this gap, the hospital established a dedicated rare disease fund under the Ramathibodi Foundation. This fund relies primarily on philanthropic donations and support generated through advocacy and community engagement initiatives.

The fund is managed through a transparent internal governance process requiring joint authorization by designated signatories, while financial operations are monitored by the hospital and the Ramathibodi Foundation's accounting department. Donations are directed to the Foundation and earmarked specifically for rare disease services. This blended public-philanthropic funding model plays an essential role in enabling access to advanced diagnostics and supporting patients facing financial barriers.

Toward achieving institutional recognition as a center of excellence

Thailand currently lacks a formal national accreditation system for rare disease centers of excellence. Despite this, Ramathibodi Hospital is widely recognized as one of the country's leading centers for rare disease diagnosis and care.

In 2019, Thailand's National Health Security Office designated seven supertertiary hospitals as national rare disease centers within the framework of the national policy on inborn errors of metabolism. These centers were selected primarily based on clinical capacity, including the availability of trained clinical geneticists. These designated centers are authorized to approve referrals for genetic testing and treatments under the Universal Coverage system and act as regional referral hubs. Ramathibodi Hospital oversees Region 9, providing services for approximately five million people across four provinces, and part of Bangkok. The hospital is currently working toward achieving formal institutional recognition as a center of excellence.

Care Delivery According to Patient Needs and Clinical Specialties

Ramathibodi Hospital provides a comprehensive range of diagnostic and clinical services for rare genetic diseases through collaboration between Pediatrics, Internal Medicine, Obstetrics and Gynecology (Maternal Fetal Medicine), and Pathology. Diagnostic services include chromosome analysis, chromosomal microarray, molecular testing (including whole exome sequencing), biochemical testing, and expanded newborn screening. Clinical geneticists serve as the main point of patient evaluation, coordinating diagnostic interpretation and care planning. Referral pathways are structured by clinical complexity: targeted cases are often referred to Pathology, while complex or undiagnosed cases are managed within pediatric genetics services. Biochemical testing and newborn screening are jointly delivered by Pathology and Pediatrics, with laboratory processing supported by Pathology and interpretation led by clinical geneticists. Multidisciplinary clinics support integrated care, including metabolic clinics with nutritional specialists and dermatology collaborations for rare skin conditions, alongside referrals to other specialties. Care models vary by patient needs. Complex conditions requiring close monitoring are managed through center-based care, while stable patients may be followed through telemedicine and shared-care arrangements with regional hospitals.

Building Capacity for Genetic Counselling and Patient Support

Thailand currently lacks a formal national training programme in genetic counselling. Ramathibodi Hospital, together with the Medical Genetics and Genomics Association (MGGA), has played a key role in addressing this workforce gap by developing 4-month short-course training programmes for nurses and healthcare professionals involved in patient support and education, since 2022.

The hospital has recently been successful in establishing a Master's degree programme in genetic counselling under Mahidol University, first cohort of students will begin their studies in August 2026.

Patient engagement is supported through close collaboration with patient organizations. While formal governance structures for patient involvement are still developing, the center maintains strong partnerships with advocacy groups, including support for establishing new patient organizations and developing educational materials. Families requiring additional support are referred to hospital social services and connected to peer support networks to address psychosocial needs.

Turning Research into Action: Data, Innovation, and Policy Impact

Research is a central component of Ramathibodi's rare disease strategy, spanning epidemiology, translational research, and health technology assessment. The center conducts disease-specific studies and contributes to functional genomics, including the identification of novel candidate genes. Health technology assessment work has informed national reimbursement decisions and supported the expansion of Thailand's rare disease benefit package. The center continues to advocate for broader access to advanced genomic diagnostics, particularly exome sequencing for undiagnosed cases. Ramathibodi also participates in several national registries, including the Universal Coverage registry for inborn metabolic disorders and disease-specific registries for conditions such as neurofibromatosis, spinal muscular atrophy, and Duchenne muscular dystrophy, supporting clinical care, research, and policy planning.

Connecting Expertise: National Leadership in Rare Disease Care

Ramathibodi Hospital is a core member of Thailand's national rare disease network, working with six other hospitals to coordinate referrals and specialist services across regions. It also serves as a regional hub for newborn screening and supports providers through specialist consultation. The hospital participates in the Genomics Thailand initiative, including its programme on undiagnosed rare diseases, and leads the Extended Rare Disease Center Model: Bridging Clinical Genetics to Regional Communities (ExtRA) operational research initiative, which strengthens collaboration with regional hospitals and supports multidisciplinary genomic case discussions. International collaboration occurs mainly through professional exchanges and case consultations with institutions in Australia and Taiwan, enabling knowledge sharing and access to global expertise.

HUMAN GENETICS AND GENOME RESEARCH INSTITUTE, NATIONAL RESEARCH CENTRE - CAIRO, EGYPT

The Human Genetics and Genome Research Institute (HGGR) is part of Egypt's National Research Centre, a large governmental academic body comprising multiple institutes across scientific disciplines. HGGR functions as the country's primary academic institute dedicated to human genetics and genetic disorders and plays a central role in rare disease diagnosis, and research in Egypt. Although not formally designated as a national rare disease center within a structured policy framework, the institute operates as a tertiary referral hub receiving patients from across the country.

A Governmental Research Institute Providing Diagnostic Services

HGGR is funded primarily through government. Research activities are supported through national competitive grants, including those from the National Research Centre (NRC) itself, the Academy of Scientific Research and Technology, and the Science, Technology and Innovation Funding Authority. Additional resources are generated through paid clinical and laboratory services delivered to the public via the affiliated Centre of Excellence for Medical Services. Revenue from these services is partially reinvested into research and service development within the institute. Private philanthropy exists but remains limited in the Egyptian context.

Although Egypt does not currently have a national system formally designating rare disease centers of excellence, HGGR received internal recognition as a Center of Excellence in Human Genetics through a competitive institutional grant process. Regular internal audits conducted by the NRC assess quality of performance, documentation, and operational standards across all institutes.

From General Genetics to Specialized Rare Disease Care

HGGR initially operated as a general genetics clinic but has progressively evolved toward a subspecialized service structure reflecting the rapid expansion of genomic medicine. Today, the institute hosts multiple specialized clinics organized around groups of genetic and rare conditions.

These include neurogenetics services covering congenital brain anomalies, neurodegenerative disorders, and neuromuscular diseases, as well as disorders of sexual development, skeletal dysplasia and limb malformations, intellectual disability and speech disorders, rare genodermatoses, hereditary blood disorders and congenital heart disease genetics. The institute is also expanding into new areas, including ophthalmo-genetics and onco-genetics. These clinical services are supported by a broad diagnostic infrastructure including molecular genetics, cytogenetics, biochemical genetics, enzymology, immunogenetics, and dental genetics laboratories. The institute also provides genetic counselling, including prenatal and preconception counselling services.

A National and Regional Role in Rare Disease Care

HGGRI receives referrals from across Egypt through multiple pathways, including primary healthcare services, specialist clinicians, insurance systems, and other hospitals. While HGGRI is not structured around a single integrated multidisciplinary team, it benefits from its location within the NRC, where multiple health-related institutes and diagnostic services are co-located. This allows access to radiology, cardiology, laboratory testing, and other clinical services within the same institutional environment. For certain complex conditions, such as neurofibromatosis, the institute is actively working toward more structured multidisciplinary care models. Currently, geneticists in the general clinic act as coordinators, triaging patients to appropriate subspecialty clinics and guiding diagnostic pathways. After diagnosis, follow-up schedules vary depending on clinical needs. Patients receiving targeted therapies are monitored closely, while those receiving symptomatic management typically attend follow-up visits every six to twelve months. In the absence of a national electronic health record or centralized registry, patient tracking is managed through an internal institutional registry. In addition to serving patients from across Egypt, the institute also provides support to patients from other countries in the region. International requests typically occur through professional networks, foundations, or conference contacts, and may involve remote counselling, diagnostic interpretation, or in-person consultations when feasible.

Collaborating with NGOs to Expand Patient Support

Patient engagement and support structures in Egypt remain limited but are gradually developing. HGGRI collaborates with several disease-specific charities and NGOs, which often provide services beyond what public institutions can offer. One notable initiative involved a metabolic clinic supporting families of children with phenylketonuria (PKU), where parents were trained to prepare specialized low-protein foods and generate income through small-scale production. The institute also collaborates closely with the Epidermolysis Bullosa patient organization in Egypt and has further launched a new awareness initiative to improve understanding of genetics and genetic disorders, showcase the productivity of people living with rare diseases, and support their engagement with NGOs involved in job training and employment opportunities. More recently, HGGRI has worked to bring together scientists, NGOs, and policymakers through conferences and awareness events, aiming to foster dialogue and identify practical ways to strengthen support for patients and families. Access to psychological support remains limited within the governmental system, but NGOs are increasingly helping to address this need and provide complementary support to patients and families.

A Strong Research Hub with Global Reach

Research is a central pillar of HGGRI's mission. The institute conducts genetic and clinical research supported by national grants and participates in international collaborations where possible. A dedicated clinical trials unit exists within the NRC, and all studies undergo review by institutional and, when required, national ethics committees. HGGRI maintains internal patient registries but does not yet participate in national or international rare disease registries, largely due to cross-border data sharing and the absence of a national rare disease registry infrastructure. Despite these constraints, the institute maintains an extensive network of international collaborations. These include partnerships within Africa, Europe, and global genomics initiatives, as well as participation in professional networks and research consortia. Collaboration often relies on personal professional links rather than formal national structures, reflecting the broader stage of rare disease system development in the country. HGGRI also contributes to training and capacity building, welcoming clinicians from other countries for laboratory training when funding is available and providing remote counselling or diagnostic support for international patients when feasible.

GILLETTE CHILDREN'S HOSPITAL – ST. PAUL, MINNESOTA, USA

Gillette Children's is an independent, not-for-profit specialty hospital in Minnesota, USA with a mission focused on rare, complex, and traumatic conditions. Rather than operating as a general health system, Gillette is structured around high-complexity pediatric care, and rare disease care is embedded across the institution's core clinical activity.

Recognition through disease-specific and quality certifications

Gillette's operations are funded primarily through revenue from patient services, complemented by a research arm supported by grant funding and a foundation that raises private philanthropic funds. Patient care financing reflects the broader U.S. system, combining government payers and commercial insurance. Gillette is not currently designated by a national authority as an official "rare disease center." Instead, the center's

Rare is our everyday!

recognition is mainly reflected through a range of disease-specific and quality-related certifications, which provide a practical way to demonstrate clinical expertise, care quality, and coordination capacity. Examples include the Spine Institute's certification, as well as condition-specific recognitions linked to spina bifida (through the Spina Bifida Association) and Rett syndrome, among others.

Importantly, these certifications represent more than reputational markers. They serve as mechanisms that connect Gillette to wider learning communities through shared practices and peer exchange, enable participation in registries, such as those supporting spina bifida care and research, and increase visibility for families seeking specialized services. Overall, the criteria for these recognitions are less dependent on reaching a specific patient-volume threshold and instead focus on demonstrating an appropriate combination of specialized services, effective multidisciplinary coordination, and adherence to evolving best practices, including clear policies, team composition, and evidence-informed protocols.

Continuity and Coordination at the Heart of Care Delivery

Gillette structures rare disease care around the principle of reducing fragmentation and minimizing the burden of repeated visits for families. Care is organized through team-based clinics designed to deliver as much coordinated input as possible within a single visit, allowing professionals to align in real time and develop shared care plans.

The hospital operates a broad portfolio of multidisciplinary clinics, including programmes for neuromuscular and movement disorders, as well as condition-specific clinics for Rett syndrome, spina bifida, and osteogenesis imperfecta.

While the exact composition of teams varies across clinics, visits commonly involve physicians, nurses, and nurse practitioners, alongside physical and occupational therapists, dietitians, genetic counselors, social workers, respiratory therapists, child life specialists, and family support professionals. Surgical specialties, dentistry, and on-site scheduling staff are included when relevant, ensuring that follow-up appointments and next steps are arranged before families leave. Continuity of care extends beyond the hospital walls, especially for children with high clinical and social complexity. Many of the greatest challenges arise after clinic visits, when care plans must be implemented across multiple providers, services, and community settings. To address this, Gillette relies on a complex care pediatric team that works closely with primary care physicians and assumes a central coordinating role across the care continuum. In this model, the complex care pediatrician functions as a single point of oversight, supported by nursing-level care coordinators. This structure compensates for limited time in primary care, fragmented delivery systems, and variable experience managing rare and complex conditions.

Patients need someone who knows the whole picture and can keep everyone moving in the same direction – someone who can act as the quarterback of the care team.

Supporting the Whole Family, Not Only the Diagnosis

Gillette's care model integrates extensive support services that address the educational, psychosocial, and financial dimensions of living with rare and complex conditions. A dedicated social work team supports families in navigating school systems, including Individualized Education Plans (IEPs), insurance processes, disability waivers, family leave approvals, and administrative requirements.

Social workers support families in accessing financial assistance, particularly when insurance coverage is limited or absent. Care coordination services help families translate complex care plans into actionable steps, reducing missed follow-up and fragmentation across services. Peer and community support is fostered through condition-specific online groups (e.g., cerebral palsy, scoliosis, spina bifida) and a range of in-person and virtual family events, from recreational activities to educational conferences. Patient and family perspectives are formally integrated through a Family Advisory Council, which provides structured input into service design and improvement priorities.

Research Anchored in Care

Gillette's research extends beyond clinical trials to include translational research, best-practice development, and longitudinal studies closely informed by clinical needs. Its patient population supports natural history studies, including disease-specific initiatives such as Rett syndrome, as well as applied research (e.g., nutritional interventions) designed for rapid translation into care delivery.

Key challenges are operational. Identifying rare disease populations within electronic medical records remains complex, particularly for patients with multiple co-existing diagnoses, and more consistent capture of genetic-level data is needed to strengthen both care planning and research readiness. Limited protected time and resources further constrain research capacity. Participation in disease-specific registries, such as those for spina bifida, supports ongoing research and quality improvement efforts.

From Local Leadership to Global Connections

Gillette plays an active role in rare disease collaboration at local, national, and international levels. In Minnesota, it contributes to newborn screening, rare disease care, and policy initiatives, while at the federal level it engages in programmes influencing care delivery and system design.

Internationally, the hospital participates in WHO-related workstreams, including rehabilitation-focused initiatives such as the World Rehabilitation Alliance—highly relevant for rare disease patients with long-term functional needs. Gillette also provides care to international patients, primarily for surgical interventions, through referrals from families, reputation-based pathways, and clinician networks. Building on this experience, it is developing more structured international collaborations to strengthen its global role in specialized care delivery.

CONCLUSION

The case studies presented in this report highlight the remarkable diversity of rare disease centers across regions, health system models, and levels of institutional maturity. Taken together, they illustrate the dedication of professionals and institutions working to improve diagnosis, care, and long-term support for people living with rare diseases and their families.

While the structure and resources of each center differ, the experiences documented here reinforce the value of sustained commitment, incremental system strengthening, and collaboration at multiple levels. They also demonstrate how meaningful progress can emerge both from formal policy initiatives and from locally driven solutions, regardless of the health system context.

Across the cases, common features and enabling factors can be observed, alongside recurring challenges and barriers. However, the intent of this report has been to present each center in its own context, highlighting its specific pathways, constraints, and innovations rather than drawing direct comparisons.

These examples are intended as sources of insight. By showcasing practical approaches, emerging innovations, and the realities faced by teams on the ground, this report aims to support ongoing efforts to build more responsive, equitable, and coordinated rare disease care globally. Ultimately, these case studies contribute to a deeper understanding of how rare disease centers are organized and how they function in practice, and they offer practical considerations that can inform future initiatives, projects, and strategies aimed at strengthening rare disease care globally.

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